

1 **The inner structure of La Fossa di Vulcano (Vulcano Island,**
2 **southern Tyrrhenian Sea, Italy) revealed by high resolution electric**
3 **resistivity tomography coupled with self-potential, temperature, and**
4 **soil CO₂ gas measurements**

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1 **Abstract.** La Fossa cone is an active stratovolcano located on Vulcano Island, in the Aeolian
2 Archipelago (southern Italy). Its activity is characterized by explosive phreatic and phreato-
3 magmatic eruptions producing wet and dry pyroclastic surges, pumice fall deposits, and
4 highly viscous lava flows. Nine profiles of 2D high resolution Electrical Resistivity
5 Tomography (ERT) (electrode spacing 20 meters, with a depth of penetration > 200 meters)
6 were performed across this edifice to image its inner structure. In addition, we also measured
7 the self-potential, the flux of CO_2 , and the temperature along these profiles. These data
8 provide complementary information to interpret the ERT profiles. The ERT profiles allow to
9 identify the main structural boundaries (and their associated fluid circulations) structuring the
10 shallow architecture of the Fossa cone. The hydrothermal system is identified by very low
11 values of the electrical resistivity ($< 20 \Omega \text{ m}$). Its lateral extension is clearly limited by the
12 crater boundaries, which are relatively resistive ($> 400 \Omega \text{ m}$). Inside the crater, it is possible to
13 follow the plumbing system of the main fumarolic area. On the flank of the edifice, a thick
14 layer of tuff is also marked by low resistivity values (in the range 1 to $20 \Omega \text{ m}$). The ashes and
15 pyroclastic materials ejected during the nineteenth Century eruptions and covering the flank
16 of the volcano corresponds to relatively resistive materials (several hundreds to several
17 thousands $\Omega \text{ m}$). We carried out perform laboratory measurements of the electrical resistivity
18 and the streaming coupling coefficient of the main materials forming the volcanic edifice. A
19 2D simulation of the ground water flow is performed over the edifice using a commercial
20 finite element code. Input parameters are the topography, the ERT cross-section, and the
21 value of the measured petrophysical parameters. From this simulation, we computed the self-
22 potential field and we found a good agreement with the computed self-potential profile and
23 the measured data. The results reveal therefore the very high potentiality of these methods for
24 high resolution modeling of the inner structure of an active volcano.
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1 **1. Introduction**

2
3 Vulcano is a small volcanic island (3 x 7 km) located at the southernmost of the
4 Aeolian Islands in the Southern Tyrrhenian Sea in Italy (38°24'N, 14°58'E) (Figure 1). It was
5 built during five main volcanic stages during the past 120,000 years. Two overlapping
6 calderas, the 2.5-km-wide Caldera del Piano on the South East and the 3-km-wide Caldera
7 della Fossa on the North West of the island, were formed at about 98,000-77,000 and 24,000-
8 13,000 years ago, respectively. Volcanism has migrated to the north of the island over time.
9 La Fossa cone, which is the target of the present investigation, occupies the 3-km-wide
10 Caldera della Fossa at the North-West end of the island (Figure 1). This edifice has been
11 active throughout the Holocene and constitutes the location of most of the historical eruptions
12 of the islands. In the vicinity of the Fossa cone, the Vulcanello edifice forms a low, roughly
13 circular peninsula on the northern tip of Vulcano (Figure 1). This area was formed as an
14 island beginning in 183 BC and was connected to Vulcano in 1550 AD during its last
15 eruption. The latest eruption from Vulcano consisted of explosive activity from the Fossa
16 cone from 1888 to 1890 (e.g., *Frazzetta et al.* [1983, 1984]).

17 There are two main reasons why we want to investigate La Fossa cone. The first
18 reason is related to the geohazards associated with the activity of the active La Fossa cone.
19 The population of the island increases up to 5,000 inhabitants during the summer and few
20 hundreds during the winter. The main geohazards at Vulcano are related to sin-eruptive
21 pyroclastic surges, bombs and block fallout, phreatic explosions, gas hazard, debris flows,
22 landslides of altered flanks and the subsequent formation of tsunamis. The second reason is
23 for its peculiarity: relatively modest dimensions and strong hydrothermal activity. The Fossa
24 cone is a perfect natural laboratory to test the ability of geophysical methods to image the
25 substructure of an active volcano. In addition, we are interested to see how geophysical
26 signals can be used to monitor changes in its activity. The recent use of deep DC electrical
27 resistivity tomography has gained in interest recently to map the substructure of volcanoes

1 and active faults (e.g., *Storz et al.* [2000]; *Colella et al.* [2004]; *Diaferia et al.* [2006];
2 *Finizola et al.* [2006]; *Nicollin et al.* [2006]; *Linde and Revil* [2007]). However, a tomography
3 of electrical resistivity alone is notoriously difficult to interpret univoquely. The main reason
4 is that electrical resistivity of volcanic rocks depends of too much parameters including the
5 water content, the salinity, the temperature, and the cation exchange capacity of the porous
6 material (e.g., *Waxman and Smits* [1968]; *Revil et al.* [2002] and references therein).
7 Therefore, it is essential to add additional information to electrical resistivity to improve the
8 interpretation of electrical resistivity tomography in terms of geological and hydrogeological
9 units (see examples in *Revil et al.* [2004b] and *Finizola et al.* [2006] at Stromboli volcano).

10 In this paper, we interpret a set of electrical resistivity tomographies crossing the Fossa
11 cone of Vulcano Island. To help the interpretation of these tomographies, additional
12 measurements of temperature, self-potential, and diffuse soil CO₂ flux from the soil were
13 carried out along the resistivity profiles. The temperature and CO₂ reveal the position of the
14 permeable pathways of the hydrothermal system. We will show that forward modeling of the
15 self-potential data can be used to constrain the pattern of the ground water. All these
16 measurements result in a unique set of data, at a kilometer scale, over an active volcano. This
17 data set reveals for the first time the inner substructure of La Fossa cone stratovolcano,
18 showing the main geological structure and the extent of the hydrothermal system inside the
19 edifice.

20

21 **2. Geological Background**

22

23 Vulcano Island represents the southernmost portion of a NW-SE elongated volcanic
24 ridge that comprises seven islands forming the Aeolian Archipelago (southern Italy). This
25 archipelago is related to the subduction of the African plate underneath the European Plate
26 [*Keller*, 1980; *Ellam et al.*, 1989]. The ridge is affected by a regional, NW-SE to N-S striking
27 fault system [*Gasparini et al.*, 1982]. In ancient times, the Romans believed that Vulcano was

1 the chimney to the forge of the god Vulcan. The glow of eruptions was thought to be from the
2 forges of the god and the island had grown because of his periodic clearing of cinders and
3 ashes. The earthquakes that either preceded or accompanied the explosions of ashes were
4 considered to be due to Vulcan himself making weapons for the other gods.

5 Nowadays, we know that the island has been shaped during five distincts stages. These
6 stages are Vulcano Primordiale, Piano Caldera, Lentia Complex, La Fossa Caldera, and
7 Vulcanello. The history of Vulcano begins with the formation of a stratovolcano. The collapse
8 of this stratovolcano produces the Piano caldera (see *Santacroce et al.* [2003]). Then, this
9 caldera was partially filled with pyroclastic deposits and lava flows. This stratovolcano and its
10 caldera form the southern part of the island of Vulcano. The Fossa cone grew within the Fossa
11 caldera, which constitutes the northern part of the island.

12 The Fossa cone is a small stratovolcano with an altitude of 391 m a.s.l. (meter above
13 sea level) (see Figures 1 and 2). The diameter of its base is about 2 kilometers. The Fossa
14 cone began to form 6,000 years ago [*Dellino and La Volpe*, 1997; *De Rosa et al.*, 2004]. Six
15 volcanic successions: Punte Nere, Palizzi, Caruggi, Forgia Vecchia, Pietre Cotte and Gran
16 Cratere (post-1739), with different vent locations and eruptive histories, build the cone
17 [*Dellino and La Volpe*, 1997; *De Rosa et al.*, 2004, *De Astis et al.*, 2007]. Each succession
18 seems to follow the same evolution starting with pyroclastic surges and ended with the
19 emission of highly viscous lava flows. All the explosive and effusive products of La Fossa
20 cone have high potassium contents and a chemical composition ranging from trachytic to the
21 more evolved rhyolitic composition [*Keller*, 1980].

22 The last eruption of the Fossa cone occurred from 1888 to 1890. In the same century,
23 Vulcano produced three eruptions lasted more than one month (1822-23, 1873, and 1886).
24 The violence of the last eruption (1888-1890) was marked by the fall of volcanic bombs and
25 blocks, about ~1 m in diameter, at ~1 km from the vent. Breadcrust bombs, distinctive of this
26 style of eruption, were ejected about half-way. These bombs are characterized by an aphyric

1 glassy matrix of rhyolitic composition and xenoliths of trachytic composition with a
2 maximum abundance of 8 vol.% [De Fino *et al.*, 1991]. Explosions were intermittent and
3 separated by quiet periods lasting a few minutes to a few days. Explosions varied in strength.
4 Only the largest explosions could throw blocks and bombs. Strong eruptions were separated
5 by longer quiet periods. No domes or lava flows were produced at the end of the eruption.
6 The peculiarity of La Fossa volcano is the occurrence of thermal and seismic crisis. The last
7 one occurred in 2004-2006 (Granieri *et al.* [2006]; Aubert *et al.* [2007]). It was characterized
8 by: strong increases of the temperature of the fumaroles and an increase of the surface area
9 covered by the fumarolic field. Chemical changes in the fumaroles and the occurrence of
10 shallow seismic activity were indicative of an increase of the input of magmatic fluids
11 (Granieri *et al.* [2006]). During such episodes there is no evidence of magma uprising.

12 There are three types of upper formations of the Fossa cone: (1) The former is
13 constituted of the Palizzi pumice deposit, mainly scattered along the southern slope of La
14 Fossa Cone and with a maximum thickness of 2 m at the break-in-slope of the volcano
15 [Frazzetta *et al.*, 1983]. The pumice fragments range in size from several centimeters to about
16 30 cm, with a mean value of about 10 cm. The glass matrix of the fragments has a trachytic
17 composition. (2) The latter constituting the substratum is formed by a very impermeable fine-
18 grained hydromagmatic tuff (Figure 1) and (3) the grey ashes from Gran Cratere that were
19 deposited all over the edifice during the 1888-1890 eruption.

20

21 **3. Field Investigations**

22

23 In October 2005, May 2006, and October 2006, we performed geophysical surveys
24 (electrical resistivity, self-potential, temperature, and soil CO₂ flux) that were organized along
25 nine profiles crossing the entire Fossa cone. The position of these profiles is shown on Figure
26 1. We present in this section, the methodology employed for the various measurements

27

1 3.1. Electrical Resistivity Profiles

2

3 Because of its sensitivity to the water content and to the alteration of porous materials,
 4 DC-electrical resistivity tomography is an efficient tool in complement of transient
 5 electromagnetic soundings to image active volcanoes (*Fitterman et al.* [1988]; *Zohdy and*
 6 *Bisdorf* [1990], *Lénat et al.* [2000]) DC-Electrical resistivity measurements were obtained
 7 along the nine profiles displayed in Figure 1. The measurements were performed using a set
 8 of 64 brass electrodes with a spacing of 20 meters. We use a shielded cable of 1.26 km made
 9 of 8 segments of 160 m each. Two or three roll-alongs of the electrodes were performed to
 10 complete each profile. Contact between the electrodes and the ground was improved by
 11 adding salty water at the base of each electrode to decrease the contact resistance between the
 12 ground and the electrodes. We used the Wenner array for its good signal-to-noise ratio.
 13 Reciprocity measurements (performed on one profile) show an uncertainty smaller than 7%.
 14 Dipole Dipole measurements provide usually complementary information with respect to the
 15 Wenner array. However, we did not perform such measurements because of time constraints.

16 The resistivity data were inverted with RES2DINV [*Loke and Barker, 1996*], which
 17 uses RES2DINV used the smoothness-constrained method [*deGroot-Hedlin and Constable,*
 18 *1990*] to perform the inverse problem:

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$$(\mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{J} + \alpha \mathbf{F}) \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{g} - \alpha \mathbf{F} \mathbf{r}, \quad (1)$$

23 where \mathbf{F} is a smoothing matrix, \mathbf{J} is the Jacobian matrix of partial derivatives, \mathbf{r} is a vector
 24 containing the logarithm of the model resistivity values, α is the damping factor, \mathbf{d} is the
 25 model perturbation vector, and \mathbf{g} is the discrepancy vector. The discrepancy vector, \mathbf{g} ,
 26 contains the difference between the calculated and measured apparent resistivity values. The
 27 magnitude of this vector is frequently given as a RMS (root-mean-squared) value. The
 28 algorithm seeks to reduce this quantity in an attempt to find a better model after each
 29 iteration. The model perturbation vector, \mathbf{d} , is the change in the model resistivity values

1 calculated using the above equation which normally results in an “improved” model. The
2 model parameters are the resistivity values of the model cell and the data are the measured
3 apparent resistivity values determined from Ohm’s law. The uniqueness of the solution of the
4 inverse problem is an issue here (see for example discussions in *Nicollin et al.* [2006] and
5 *Linde and Revil* [2007]). This means that for the same data set, there are several possible
6 resistivity models that fit the data equally well (e.g., *Constable et al.* [1987]; *Auken and*
7 *Christiansen* [2004]; *Binley and Kemna* [2005]). Additional information can be helpful to
8 stabilize the inversion process. Starting from an initial model, RES2DINV looks for an
9 improved model whose calculated apparent resistivity values are closer to the measured
10 values. We used various initial models to test the stability of the inversion. In the present case,
11 starting the iterations with either a uniform resistivity model or the apparent resistivity
12 pseudosection did not alter the final result.

13 Besides trying to minimize the difference between the measured and calculated
14 apparent resistivity values, the inversion method used by RES2DINV attempts to minimize
15 the roughness (i.e. the reciprocal of the model smoothness) of the model resistivity values.
16 The damping factor, α , controls the weight given to the smoothness model in the inversion
17 process. Therefore, with larger damping factor, there will be a smoother model but the
18 apparent resistivity RMS error will probably be larger.

19 Topography was also included in the inversion process. Topography was extracted
20 from a very precise digital elevation map (DEM of 1x1m) of La Fossa cone provided by
21 Maria Marsella (see also *Baldi et al.* [2002]). Northing and Easting UTM coordinates were
22 obtained from a portable GPS receiver. Four electrical resistivity tomographies are displayed
23 in Figures 3 to 6. Accounting for the complex geometry of the volcano, a 3D inversion of
24 ERT would be necessary to define the complex structural heterogeneities of the Fossa edifice.
25 However, we show below that 2D inversion of ERT provides already an image that is
26 consistent with the other data (self-potential, temperature, and CO₂) in order to define the

1 architecture of the volcano.

2

3 **3.2. Temperature**

4

5 Thermal probes and a digital thermometer were used to measure the temperature of the
6 ground. Each temperature measurement was done in four steps. (1) A hole is dug to a depth of
7 30 ± 2 cm with a steel rod (2 cm in diameter). (2) A thermal probe is inserted into the hole at
8 the precise depth of 30 ± 1 cm by means of a graduated wooden stick. (3) The hole is filled
9 and compacted. (4) After 10 to 15 minutes (this duration is required to achieve thermal
10 equilibrium), a temperature reading is performed (see *Finizola et al.* [2003]).

11 The temperature profile provides an independent way to see the extension of the
12 hydrothermal body in the vicinity of the ground surface. The temperature was measured with
13 a sensitivity of 0.2 °C. Due to the maximum amplitude of diurnal variation at Vulcano at 30
14 cm depth during summer season (1.2°C), and due to the maximum amplitude of seasonal
15 variation, from 12.2 to 27.2°C respectively in January and August (*Lo Cascio and Navarra*
16 [1997]), we consider a temperature above 30°C can be consider as indicative of the
17 underground geothermal system. No correction has been applied on the temperature data set,
18 because the temperature correction should also integrate shallow hydrothermal areas where
19 fluids rise. In these conditions of both conductive and convective heat supply, traditional
20 thermal conductive corrections are not easy to apply. A map of the interpolated temperature is
21 shown on Figure 7.

22 It is important to note that our temperature measurements were obtained at different
23 periods during the last 2004-2006 crisis, which began in November 2004 (*Granieri et al.*,
24 [2006]). As a consequence, the amplitude of the temperature anomalies could be higher than
25 the amplitude during the intercrisis periods. In this aspect, the amplitude the anomalies is not
26 of a first importance because we will use temperature anomalies as a way to detect
27 qualitatively preferential fluid flow pathways in the hydrothermal system.

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2 **3.3. CO₂ Soil Flux**

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4 The CO₂ soil flux measurements were obtained with a spacing of 20 m (uncertainty <
5 5 %). The methodology is described in details in *Chiodini et al.* [1998]. The accumulation
6 chamber method allows to measure quickly the CO₂ fluxes from the soil in a wide interval
7 from 0.2 to over 104 g/(m² day). This method does not require corrections or assumptions on
8 the characteristics of the soil. The instrumentation consists in an IR spectrometer, to measure
9 CO₂ fluxes from 0 to 2000 μmol/mol (2 % vol.), an accumulation chamber (type A: dead
10 volume 30 cm³) and a palmtop to plot the CO₂ increase. The accumulation chamber is leaned
11 on the ground so that the atmospheric air can not penetrate inside. The gas permeating from
12 the soil accumulates in the dead volume, thus the CO₂ concentration increases; every second
13 the gas is analyzed by the IR spectrometer and reinjected in the accumulation chamber not to
14 deplete the carbon dioxide concentration. The palmtop software shows the increase of the
15 concentration vs. time in real time and the software allows to calculate immediately the slope
16 of this trend in ppm/s. This slope is directly proportional to the flux of CO₂ from the soil,
17 expressed in g/(m² d), by a constant depending on the instrument dead volume and on the
18 atmospheric pressure.

19 Carbon dioxide anomalies have their origin in magma degassing inside the volcanic
20 system. The gas follows the same preferential pathways that the hydrothermal fluids
21 providing information about the permeability distribution of the edifice. High fluxes evidence
22 therefore permeable pathways.

23

24 **3.4. Self-potential**

25

26 The self-potential (SP) method consists in measuring the distribution of the electric
27 potential at the surface of the Earth with respect to a reference electrode (e.g., *Corwin and*

1 Hoover [1979]; Lénat [2007]). Sources of self-potential fields include large-scale Earth
2 currents due to ionospheric activity, chemical potential gradients (Maineult *et al.* [2005,
3 2006]), redox potentials (Linde and Revil [2007]), and fluid movement in porous materials
4 through the so-called streaming potential. In active volcanoes, the main source of self-
5 potential anomalies is related to the flow of the ground water (Massenet and Pham [1985],
6 Ishido *et al.* [1997]; Bedrosian *et al.* [2007]). This is the only method that can be used to
7 determine the pattern of ground water flow and to determine changes in the seepage velocity
8 (see Perrier *et al.* [1998], Kulesa *et al.* [2003a, b], Rizzo *et al.* [2004], Hase *et al.* [2005];
9 Titov *et al.* [2005], Suski *et al.* [2006], Wishart *et al.* [2006]).

10 To perform the self-potential measurements, we used a pair of non-polarizing
11 Cu/CuSO₄ electrodes. The microporous nature of the end-contacts of these electrodes (made
12 in a low-permeability wood) avoids leakage of the CuSO₄ solution during contact between
13 with the ground. Wood is also much more resistant than the ceramic in which a substantial
14 number of electrodes are made. The difference of electrical potential between the reference
15 electrode (arbitrarily placed at the beginning of the profile) and the moving electrode was
16 measured with a calibrated high impedance voltmeter (METRIX MX20, sensitivity of 0.1
17 mV, internal impedance of ~100 MΩ).

18 Before each series of measurements, the electrodes are put face-to-face to check that
19 the difference of potential between the two electrodes is less than 2 mV. At each station, a
20 small hole (~10 cm deep) was dug to improve the electrical contact between the electrode and
21 the ground. For each self-potential measurement, the value of the electrical resistance was
22 also measured prior the self-potential measurement. The moisture in the soil was most of the
23 time sufficiently high to make the impedance contact between the electrode and the ground
24 low enough to get good measurements. However, if the contact resistance was high (>1 MΩ),
25 a small amount of a saturated CuSO₄ solution was placed at the bottom of the hole to decrease
26 the contact resistance. A long wire was used to connect the two electrodes. The distance

1 between two successive measurements was 20 m. The total length of the wire was 400 m, and
2 consequently, 20 measurements were realized with the same reference. The advantage of this
3 procedure is to avoid cumulative errors by changing the reference too often along the same
4 profile. Every 400 m, a new reference station was settled. As the profiles were several
5 kilometers long, several base stations were used to cover the entire profiles. At the end of the
6 profile, the entire self-potential profile was reconstructed using the first reference station as
7 the unique reference for the entire profile.

8

9 **4. Laboratory Measurements**

10

11 In this section, we report laboratory measurements of the electrical conductivity and
12 streaming potential of a collection of core samples from the edifices of La Fossa di Vulcano
13 and Stromboli. Electrical conductivity measurements were performed on each sample at
14 different frequencies (in the range 20 Hz to 100 kHz), at $20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ (room temperature), and at
15 the following pore fluid conductivities $\sigma_f = 0.1 \text{ S m}^{-1}$ and 0.5 S m^{-1} (NaCl, pH 7). The
16 conductivity of the pore water sampled at the base of the volcano in different wells is in the
17 range 0.1 to 2.8 S m^{-1} and the pH is in the range 5.4 to 7.9 with a mean equal to 6.7 (*Cortesi et*
18 *al.* [2001]). We believe therefore that 0.1 S m^{-1} corresponds to the fresh water pole while high
19 conductivities are indicative of a mixture of this pole with the sea water. The water flowing
20 along the slopes affected by fumarolic fields is also enriched with the fumarolic acid
21 condensates coming from the pericrateric high-temperature fumaroles along the preferred
22 pathways highlighted by the resistivity tomographies.

23 We use a WayneKerr-6425 impedancemeter for the resistivity measurement. This
24 impedancemeter was first calibrated in short and open circuits. The samples were placed
25 between two stainless steel electrodes. Two circular brine-saturated paper filters were used to
26 get good electrical contacts between the sample and these electrodes. Prior the measurements,
27 the jacketed samples were dried at 60°C during 2 days and then saturated with the degassed

1 brine at 0.1 S m^{-1} . Between the electrical conductivity measurements, the salinity of the brine
 2 was changed by placing the samples in an electrolyte at 0.5 S m^{-1} and by letting the salt
 3 diffusing inside the sample through the two end-faces during 1 week. Then, a new set of
 4 electrical conductivity measurements were performed. The results are reported in Table 1.

5 Electrical conductivity is sensitive to the water content, the mineralization of the pore
 6 water (salinity), the cation exchange capacity of the clay minerals (surface conductivity), and
 7 temperature (see *Waxman and Smits* [1968], *Revil et al.* [1998, 2002], *Niwas et al.* [2007]; *Jin*
 8 *et al.* [2007]; *Shevvin et al.* [2007]). In this paper, we use a simple linear conductivity model,
 9

$$10 \quad \sigma = \frac{1}{F} [\sigma_f + (F - 1)\sigma_s], \quad (2)$$

11
 12 which can be considered as a first-order approximation of the non-linear models proposed by
 13 *Revil et al.* [1998, 2002]. In Equation (2), F is the electrical formation factor and σ_s is the
 14 surface conductivity occurring in the Stern layer at the water / mineral interface. Surface
 15 conductivity usually results from the cation exchange capacity of clay minerals and zeolites
 16 and is indicative of the alteration of the rock (see *Roberts and Lin* [1997]; *Revil et al.* [2002];
 17 *Bernard et al.* [2007]). Using Eq. (2) and the resistivity data reported in Table 1, we
 18 determined the value of the formation factor and surface conductivity. These values are
 19 reported in Table 2. We note that the tuff of Vulcano is characterized by a very high surface
 20 conductivity, which explains the very low electrical resistivity observed by the resistivity
 21 surveys for this formation (see Figures 2 to 6).

22 In addition to the electrical conductivity measurements, we also performed
 23 measurements of the streaming potential coupling coefficient C at room temperature ($20 \pm$
 24 2°C). The streaming potential coupling coefficient is the key-material property required to
 25 compute the self-potential contribution associated with ground water flow (see Section 5
 26 below) (e.g., *Tosha et al.* [2003]). The experimental setup for the measurement of the
 27 streaming potential coupling coefficient is shown Figure 8. A given hydraulic head is imposed

1 on the cylindrical sample placed at the bottom of the tube by adding water to the water
 2 column in the tube in such a way that the hydraulic head is maintained constant above the
 3 rock sample. The gradient of the fluid pressure is controlled by the hydraulic head in the tube
 4 and the length of the sample. The electrical potential resulting from the flow of the pore water
 5 is measured with two non-polarizable Ag/AgCl₂ electrodes (Ref321/XR300, Radiometer
 6 Analytical) located in the vicinity of the end-faces of the sample (Figure 8). The difference of
 7 the electrical potential measured between the end-faces of the porous pack divided by the
 8 length of the sample is the streaming electrical field associated with the flow of the brine
 9 through the sample. The voltages are measured with a voltmeter (Metrix MX-20, internal
 10 impedance 100 MΩ, sensitivity of 0.1 mV).

11 In viscous laminar flow conditions, the differences of the electrical potential measured
 12 in the vicinity of the end-faces of the porous medium are proportional to the imposed
 13 hydraulic heads (Figure 9). The slope of the linear trend of streaming potential vs. head is the
 14 streaming potential coupling coefficient,
 15

$$16 \quad C = \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial H} \right)_{j=0} . \quad (3)$$

17
 18 Values of the streaming potential coupling coefficient are reported in Table 1.

19 After completion of the electrical conductivity and streaming potential measurements,
 20 we determined the porosity and matrix density from classical triple weight measurements.
 21 The samples were first washed with demineralized water during 1 week to let the salt
 22 diffusing out from the samples. Then the samples were dried at 60°C for 4 days and their
 23 weights measured. Finally, the samples were saturated with degassed water under vacuum and
 24 let for 2 additional days for complete saturation of the connected porosity by water. Weight
 25 measurements of the saturated samples were carried out after that time. The weight of the
 26 saturated samples was measured with the samples immersed in water (buoyancy weight).
 27 Values of the porosity are reported in Table 2. A correlation between the formation factors

1 and the connected porosities (not shown here) indicates that the formation factor is related to
2 the porosity by an Archie's law $F = \phi^{-m}$ with $m \approx 2.0 \pm 0.1$.

3

4 **5. Interpretation and Discussion**

5

6 In this section, we interpret the electrical resistivity, CO₂, self-potential, and
7 temperature measurements in terms of pattern of the ground water flow inside the edifice.

8

9 **5.1. The Flanks**

10

11 Along the East-West direction (see Profile 1 for example), we observe a simple
12 geometrical pattern for the electrical resistivity data. A resistive ash layer (100-1000 Ω m)
13 covers a tuff layer of low resistivity (5 to 50 Ω m, see Figures 3 and 10). At depth, a highly
14 and continuous resistive body is observed on both sides of the volcano (Figures 3 and 10). We
15 interpret this body as corresponding to massive lava flow units with resistivity in the range
16 100 to 5000 Ω m. No thermal anomalies are observed at the ground surface along the flanks.
17 The self-potentials exhibit a classical W-shape (*Ishido* [2004]). This shape is traditionally
18 interpreted as the effect of the upwelling of hydrothermal fluids in the central part of the
19 edifice and the downward flow of meteoritic groundwater along the flanks of the edifice
20 (*Michel and Zlotnicki* [1998], *Revil et al.* [2003]). This self-potential anomaly will be
21 quantitatively modelled in Section 6 using a commercial finite-element code accounting for
22 both ground water flow and the resistivity pattern, which influences the equipotential lines
23 generated by the electrokinetic conversion of ground water flow.

24 Profile 3 is nearly perpendicular to Profile 1 (see Figure 4). This profile shows a very
25 complex pattern by comparison with Profile 1 and the existence of thermal anomalies
26 resulting from the evolution of the volcano over time (see Figure 4). It crosses in the northern
27 part of the profile, temperature anomalies related to the crater boundaries of Forgia Vecchia..
28 The first (and the most important) of the two Forgia Vecchia craters, Forgia Vecchia I, was

1 formed VI Century B.C. (*Giacomelli and Scandone* [2002]). The second crater, Forgia
2 Vecchia II, was formed in 1727 A.D. (*Frazzetta and La Volpe* [1991]), just before the
3 extrusion of the Pietre Cotte obsidian lava flow that occurred in 1739 A.D. (*De Fiore* [1922]).
4

5 **5.2. The Hydrothermal System**

6

7 Fumarolic activity indicates that the extension of the hydrothermal system is
8 constrained by the boundary of the main crater, except for the area of Forgia Vecchia. The
9 map of the temperature (Figure 7) shows that the main structural morphological crater
10 boundaries, evidenced by previous geological surveys, are used as preferential fluid flow
11 pathways for the upwelling of the hot fluids. These structural boundaries are: (1) the southern
12 crater rim of Caruggi cycle (*De Astis et al.*, 2007) representing the ex-Commenda cycle (2)
13 the Fossa I crater rim located in the eastern part of the edifice. (3) Different imbricated crater
14 boundaries constituting the present day fumarolic cone of Vulcano also called La Fossa cone
15 or Gran Cratere (post-1739), (4) more a small temperature pic on Forgia Vecchia crater rim,
16 in the northern part of the edifice. That means clearly that all the geological crater boundaries
17 constituting the actual cone of Vulcano edifice, act as preferential drain for heated
18 hydrothermal fluids. The hydrothermal system is mainly contained inside the boundary of the
19 craters including Forgia Vecchia. All the crater boundaries correspond indeed to thermal
20 anomalies with respect to the background near-surface temperature (Figure 7). These
21 boundaries are planes of mechanical weakness along which the cracks are periodically reopen
22 by the tectonic activity of the volcano during the crisis affecting la Fossa di Vulcano (see
23 *Granieri et al.* [2006]).

24 Figure 11 shows the architecture of the Fossa cone along a SW-NE profile. The area of
25 the highest temperature fumarolic activity (noted “F” in figure 11) can be extended to a depth
26 of 200 meters corresponding to a conductive region. The high conductivity of this region is

1 probably related to the presence of alteration products (clays and zeolites) combined with the
 2 high temperatures inside this zone (see *Lénat et al.* [2000]; *Revil et al.* [2003]; *Bernard et al.*
 3 [2007]).

4 Below the sea level, high conductivity associated with the intrusion of the brines from
 5 the sea can explain the disappearance of some of the structures below the sea level (e.g., on the
 6 right-hand side of Profile 1 , see Figure 3). Therefore, when interpreting resistivity profiles,
 7 we have to keep in mind that the relationship between resistivity and lithology is non-
 8 univoque.

10 **5.3. Flow Pattern at Vulcano**

11
 12 Recently several finite-difference and finite-element codes have been developed or
 13 used to model the distribution of the electrical streaming potential resulting from the flow of
 14 the ground water (see *Berube* [2007]; *Bolève et al.* [2007]; *Sheffer and Oldenburg* [2007]).
 15 Such numerical simulations can be used to assess the geometry of ground water flow of
 16 volcanoes and geothermal systems (*Revil et al.* [1999]; *Ishido and Pritchett* [1999]). The
 17 physics of these streaming potential can be explained as follows. The existing charge at the
 18 surface of the minerals in contact with water is counterbalanced by an excess of electrical
 19 charges located in the pore water. Therefore streaming potentials are electrical potentials
 20 resulting from the drag of the excess of electrical charge contained in the pore water.

21 In this section, we use the resistivity profile measured along the East-West profile to
 22 simulate ground water flow along this profile and to compute the resulting self-potential
 23 profile. Using the recent model developed by *Revil et al.* [2005] and *Revil and Linde* [2006],
 24 the total current density \mathbf{j} (in A m⁻²) is given by,

$$26 \quad \mathbf{j} = \sigma \mathbf{E} + \bar{Q}_v \mathbf{u}, \quad (4)$$

27

1 where \mathbf{u} is the Darcy's velocity (in m s^{-1}), $\mathbf{E} = -\nabla\phi$ is the macroscopic electrical field (in V
 2 m^{-1}), ϕ is the electrical (self-) potential (in V), and \bar{Q}_v is the excess of charge (of the diffuse
 3 layer) of the pore water per unit pore volume (in C m^{-3}). The streaming potential coupling
 4 coefficient defined by Eq. (3) and the excess of charge \bar{Q}_v are related to each other and to the
 5 hydraulic conductivity K (in m s^{-1}) by $C = \partial\phi/\partial H = -\bar{Q}_v K / \sigma$ (Revil *et al.* [2005]).

6 According to Eq. (4), the distribution of the self-potential is sensitive to the pattern of
 7 the Darcy velocity \mathbf{u} . Therefore, the mechanism generating the flow itself (gravitational flow,
 8 free or forced convection) is rather unimportant regarding the distribution of the self-potential
 9 signals. We determine the flow pattern by using Darcy's law:

$$10 \quad \mathbf{u} = -K\nabla H, \quad (5)$$

11
 12 where $\Delta H = \delta p / \rho_f g$ is the change in hydraulic head (above or below the hydrostatic initial
 13 distribution H_0), δp is the excess of pressure above or below the hydrostatic level, ρ_f is the
 14 pore fluid density (in kg m^{-3}), and g is the acceleration of the gravity (in m s^{-2}). The Darcy's
 15 law is combined with the continuity equation for the mass of the pore fluid is:

$$16 \quad S \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (K\nabla H), \quad (6)$$

17
 18 where t is time, S is the poro-elastic storage coefficient at saturation. The following
 19 computation is performed in steady state conditions and therefore the flow is given by
 20 solving $\nabla \cdot (K\nabla H) = 0$. The flow can be imposed by using appropriate boundary conditions
 21 and conservation of the flux of the pore water. Here, we impose the flux at the boundaries of
 22 the system.

23
 24 The continuity equation for the electrical charge is $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{j} = 0$. Combining this equation
 25 with Eq. (4) results in a Poisson equation with a source term that depends only on the seepage
 26 velocity in the ground:

$$27 \quad \nabla \cdot (\sigma \nabla \phi) = \mathfrak{S}, \quad (7)$$

28
 29
 30

1 where \mathfrak{S} is the volumetric current source density (in A m^{-3}) given by,

$$2 \quad 3 \quad 4 \quad \mathfrak{S} = \overline{Q}_v \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} + \nabla \overline{Q}_v \cdot \mathbf{u}, \quad (8)$$

5 The resistivity distribution determined along profile 1 (see Figure 3) was imported into
 6 the commercial finite-element software “Comsol Multiphysics 3.3”. The resistivity cross-
 7 section was discretized in several blocks (each block was then discretized using triangular
 8 meshing). The blocks comprised the ashes, the tuff, the inner massive lava flow units, and the
 9 hydrothermal system. In addition to the value of the resistivity, we need the values of the
 10 permeability and the streaming current coupling coefficient plus boundary conditions for the
 11 current density or the electrical potential and the hydraulic charge or the flux of water to
 12 determine the flow of the ground water in steady-state conditions. We use $C = -5 \text{ mV m}^{-1}$ and
 13 $k = 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$ for the ashes, $C = -3 \text{ mV m}^{-1}$ and $k = 10^{-14} \text{ m}^2$ for the tuff, $C = -5 \text{ mV m}^{-1}$ and $k =$
 14 10^{-11} m^2 for the hydrothermal system. We assign a null permeability to the massive lava flow
 15 units and therefore the coupling coefficient in this unit does not matter.

16 The pattern of ground water flow we simulated is shown on Figure 12. There is a
 17 downward flow inside the ashes and the tuff materials along the flanks of the volcano while
 18 there is an upward flow inside the boundary of the crater. As shown from the CO_2 data, there
 19 is no seal inside the crater (except maybe at the bottom part of the crater). The upward flow of
 20 the hot pore water is responsible from a strong evaporation of the water inside the boundaries
 21 of the crater. To check if this pattern of ground water flow is compatible with the self-
 22 potential data, we determine the resulting self-potential distribution along Profile 1. The
 23 simulated self-potential profile agrees quite well with the measured self-potential profile. In
 24 turn, this means that we could invert the measured self-potential data to determine the
 25 distribution of the Darcy velocity of the water phase inside the edifice. This will be the goal of
 26 a future research work.

27

28 **6. Concluding Statements**

29

1 The inner structure of La Fossa di Vulcano (Vulcano Island, southern Tyrrhenian Sea,
2 Italy) is revealed by high resolution electric resistivity tomography coupled with self-
3 potential, temperature, and CO₂ gas flux measurements. These measurements provide an idea
4 of the architecture of the edifice including the geometry of the ashes, the tuff, the lava flow
5 units, and the organization of the hydrothermal system. Numerical modelling with Comsol
6 Multiphysics 3.3 along the East-West profile shows the downward percolation of water in the
7 ashes and the tuff, and upward flow of the ground water inside the crater that is required to
8 explain the observed self-potential data measured along this profile.

9 Because of its relatively small size and importance in terms of geohazards, La Fossa di
10 Vulcano is a very suitable natural laboratory to see how various geophysical methods can be
11 integrated to reveal the architecture of a volcano and to monitor its thermohydronechanical
12 behavior. In the near-future, we plan to perform a three dimensional joint inversion of
13 electrical resistivity and gravity data. Such joint inversion would probably be very helpful to
14 invert the structural discontinuities of the edifice and to get density and resistivity values for
15 each sub-unit.

16
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1 **Table 1.** Measurements of the electrical resistivity, the streaming potential coupling
 2 coefficient of various samples from Stromboli and La Fossa di Vulcano (called respectively
 3 “S-“ and “V-“). S-Bi: Vancori Basalt (Stromboli), S-LFi: Lava Flow (Piscità, Stromboli), S-
 4 Ti: Tuff (Pizzo, Stromboli), V-LFi: Lava flow (Vulcano), V-Lbi: Lava Flow (Borehole,
 5 Vulcano) , and V-Ti: Tuff (Vulcano).

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Samples	Resistivity (in Ω m)	C (in mV m ⁻¹)	Resistivity (in Ω m)	C (in mV m ⁻¹)
	$\sigma_f = 0.1$ S m ⁻¹	$\sigma_f = 0.1$ S m ⁻¹	$\sigma_f = 0.5$ S m ⁻¹	$\sigma_f = 0.5$ S m ⁻¹
S-B1	698	-3.9	167	-1.79
S-B2	638	-2.6	192	-0.54
S-B3	707	-4.1	222	-0.75
S-LF1	802	-5.2	180	-0.90
S-LF2	728	-4.1	179	-1.71
S-LF3	421	-	53	-
S-LF4	575	-2.1	205	-0.61
S-LF5	327	-2.0	113	-1.47
S-LF6	1040	-2.4	160	-1.05
S-T1	656	-2.0	125	-0.87
S-T2	452	-2.9	102	-0.89
S-T3	626	-5.1	135	-0.62
S-T4	713	-3.4	130	-0.80
V-LF1	378	-5.4	74	-2.22
V-LF2	265	-4.2	63	-1.09
V-LF3	345	-3.4	57	-0.92
V-Lb1	227	-4.3	61	-0.91
V-Lb2	306	-2.8	55	-0.96
V-Lb3	712	-3.8	94	-0.77
V-Lb4	315	-2.5	40	-1.31
V-T1	22	-3.4	7.8	-0.12

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1 **Table 2.** Formation factor and surface conductivity determined from the electrical
 2 conductivity measurements. “S-“ and “V-“ stand for Stromboli and Vulcano samples. S-Bi:
 3 Vancori Basalt (Stromboli), S-LFi: Lava Flow (Piscità, Stromboli), S-Ti: Tuff (Pizzo,
 4 Stromboli), V-LFi: Lava flow (Vulcano), V-Lbi: Lava Flow (Borehole, Vulcano) , and V-Ti:
 5 Tuff (Vulcano).

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Samples	F	σ_s (in 10^{-4} S m^{-1})	Porosity
S-B1	90	4.3	0.15
S-B2	112	7.6	0.09
S-B3	132	7.3	0.13
S-LF1	95	2.9	0.12
S-LF2	97	4.4	0.13
S-LF3	28	9.2	0.18
S-LF4	130	10.5	0.12
S-LF5	71	18.1	0.12
S-LF6	82	1.55	0.10
S-T1	63	0.7	0.12
S-T2	54	5.3	0.12
S-T3	71	3.3	0.10
S-T4	65	0.1	0.10
V-LF1	38	2.8	0.44
V-LF2	34	11.4	0.48
V-LF3	29	3.0	0.48
V-Lb1	34	18.3	0.14
V-Lb2	28	0.4	0.14
V-Lb3	49	4.5	0.13
V-Lb4	21	12.6	0.14
V-T1	4.8	310	-

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3 **Figure 1.** Position of the investigated area on the Fossa cone, Vulcano Island (Italy). Nine
 4 profiles (labeled from 1 to 9) have been performed crossing the Fossa edifice. The bright
 5 areas on the flanks of the volcano correspond to the hydromagmatic tuff discussed in the main
 6 text.

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Figure 2. The Fossa cone such as seen from the south..

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4 **Figure 3.** Temperature, self-potential, soil CO₂ flux, and electrical resistivity tomography
 5 along Profile 1; These data show that the main activity is constrained inside the crater, which
 6 is characterized by self-potential, CO₂, and temperature anomalies. Note that the ground
 7 surface of the central part of the crater is cold.

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Figure 4. Temperature, self-potential, soil CO₂ flux, and electrical resistivity tomography along Profile 3. Note that the bottom part of the crater is cold. On the northern flank of the edifice, a conductive area is laterally limited by two thermal anomalies. These later represents the boundary of the Forgia Vecchia crater which last eruption occurred in 1727.

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3 **Figure 5.** Temperature, self-potential, soil CO₂ flux, and electrical resistivity tomography
4 along Profile 6.

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3 **Figure 6.** Temperature, self-potential, soil CO₂ flux, and electrical resistivity tomography

4 along Profile 8.

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5 **Figure 7.** Map of the temperature at a depth of 30 cm superimposed on the DEM of La Fossa
 6 cone. The white dots correspond to the location of the temperature measurements of the
 7 present study. The small white dots correspond to a detailed temperature survey (at the same
 8 depth of 30 cm) inside the La Fossa crater made by *Aubert et al.* [2007]. Note that the bottom
 9 part of the crater is mainly cold. Thermal anomalies are sometimes observed on the flanks of
 10 the volcano. In this case, these anomalies are indicative of the boundaries of ancient craters.

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Figure 8. Sketch of the experimental setup used to measure the streaming potential coupling coefficient. The jacketed sample is placed at the bottom of a Plexiglas tube. The record of the self-potentials during the flow of the electrolyte through the sample is done with Ag/AgCl electrodes (“Ref” is the reference electrode). The hydraulic heads are maintained constant at different levels and the electromotive force is recorded at these levels between the end-faces of the core sample.

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4 **Figure 9.** Examples of typical runs for different volcanic rock samples. **a.** Using a water
5 conductivity of 0.1 S m^{-1} (this value is typical of the conductivity of the water flowing in the
6 shallow aquifers). **b.** Using a water conductivity of 0.5 S m^{-1} . We observe linear relationships
7 between the variations of the streaming potentials and the variations of the hydraulic heads at
8 these two salinities. At each salinity, the streaming potential coupling coefficient is equal to
9 the slope of the linear trend. The denomination of the samples is the same as in Tables 1 and
10 2.

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- 3 **Figure 10.** Architecture of the Fossa cone along the profile 1. “Ah” and “HS” stand for
- 4 respectively Ash and Hydrothermal System. “C” and “R” stand for respectively Conductive
- 5 and Resistive body.

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4 **Figure 11.** Architecture of the Fossa cone along the profile 6. The root of the area of
 5 fumarolic activity can be extended to a depth of 200 meters below the ground surface. F:
 6 Fumaroles, Ah: Ashes, HS: Hydrothermal System. The internal part of the crater is
 7 characterized by a pocket of high conductivity (C) and a resistive structure (R).

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4 **Figure 12.** Finite element modeling of ground water flow and resulting self-potential
 5 distribution at the ground surface of the Fossa Cone using Comsol Multiphysics 3.3. The
 6 negative self-potential anomaly along the flanks of the volcan results from the percolation of
 7 the ground water in shallow aquifers while the positive self-potential anomaly inside the
 8 crater is due to the upflow of the hydrothermal fluids.

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